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IEEE Medical MHBDDT Joint Conference Keynote, Session #5*

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Automated testing of real-life self-driving systems and beyond

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9 Apr 2019, San Francisco East Bay, USA

Outline

- The “intelligence” fallacy
- The “testers can always decide” fallacy
 - Oracle problem
 - Metamorphic testing
- The “reliability” fallacy
- The “safety driver” fallacy
- More examples of detected bugs

AI baby-sits users.

Users baby-sit AI

AI baby-sits users.

- The “intelligence” fallacy

Autopilot (in aircrafts)

- The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) estimates commercial airline pilots use automation to fly 90% of the time.
- Improvements in airline automation have resulted in an impressive safety record.
 - US Dept. of Transportation

<https://www.businessinsurance.com/article/00010101/NEWS06/302289983/Flying-on-autopilot-improves-airline-safety-but-can-lead-to-errors>

Aviation safety

as a result of advances in engineering & technology

number of fatal accidents and 5-year moving average

Aviation safety

as a result of advances in engineering & technology

Z.Q. (George) Zhou, University of Wollongong

Aviation safety

as a result of advances in engineering & technology

Source:

Source:	the Aviation Safety Network database (http://aviation-safety.net)
Contact:	Harro Ranter (hr@aviation-safety.net)
Date:	3/21/2018
Rights:	CC-BY (http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
Dataset:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- accidents, including hijackings, sabotage, shoot-downs- fatal (at least on fatality among the plane's occupants)- aircraft model certified to carry 14+ passengers- includes all civil operation types (passenger, cargo, training etc.)- military flights are not included- aircraft damaged beyond repair- data since 1-1-1946

Aviation safety: the downside

The Washington Post
Democracy Dies in Darkness

Business

Boeing CEO apologizes for lives lost and acknowledges role of company's flight-control system in two crashes

In their efforts to compensate for the unreliability of human performance, the designers of automated control systems have unwittingly created opportunities for new error types that can be even more serious than those they were seeking to avoid.

- Chris Hart, Acting Chairman, National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-28002054>

“If an erroneously high **single** *angle of attack* (AOA) sensor input is received by the flight control system, there is a potential for repeated nose-down trim commands” – FAA.

How the new MAX flight-control system operates to prevent a stall

Angle of attack sensor aligns itself with oncoming air flow.

The angle of attack, the angle between the wing and the air flow, is fed into the flight computer. If it rises too high, suggesting an approaching stall, the MCAS system activates.

MCAS (Maneuvering Characteristics Augmentation System)

The MCAS system automatically swivels the horizontal tail to move the nose down. In the Lion Air crash, the angle of attack sensor fed false information to the flight computer.

Sources: Boeing, FAA, Indonesia National Transportation Safety Committee, Leeham.net, and The Air Current.

Reporting by DOMINIC GATES,
Graphic by MARK NOWLIN / THE SEATTLE TIMES

The “intelligence” fallacy
“AI baby-sits users.”

U.S. pilots flying 737 MAX weren't told about new automatic systems change linked to Lion Air crash

Originally published November 12, 2018 at 7:07 pm | Updated November 13, 2018 at 1:43 pm

The Seattle Times
Nov. 2018

WERE PILOTS GIVEN ADEQUATE TRAINING?

Short answer: no. When the Max jet was under development, regulators determined that pilots could fly the planes without extensive retraining because they were essentially the same as previous generations, [according to *The New York Times*](#). This saved Boeing a lot of money on extra training, which aided the company in its competition with Airbus to introduce newer, more fuel-efficient airplanes. The FAA **didn't change** those rules after Lion Air 610 crashed.

So rather than hours-long training sessions in giant, multimillion-dollar simulators, many pilots instead learned about the 737's new features on an iPad. Pilots at United Airlines put together a 13-page guide to the 737 Max, which did not mention the MCAS.

[According to *Reuters*](#), the doomed Lion Air cockpit voice recorder revealed how pilots scoured a manual in a losing battle to figure out why they were hurtling down to sea.

Since the crash of Ethiopian Airlines 302, that's mostly changed. On Sunday, March

***AS THE PLANE PLUMMETED,
THE DOOMED LION AIR PILOTS
SCoured A MANUAL IN A
LOSING BATTLE***

The “intelligence” fallacy
“AI baby-sits users.”

The pride of
programmers

A mean kid at school asked me if I was a nerd? I said, I preferred the term ‘smarter than you’.

The “intelligence” fallacy “AI baby-sits users.”

<http://help.bing.microsoft.com/#apex/18/en-us/10002/0>

The screenshot shows the Bing Help page. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Search Help" and a magnifying glass icon. Below the search bar, there are navigation links for "Bing", "Bing Maps", "Bing Bar", and "Bing for business". The main heading is "Advanced search options". Below the heading, there is a paragraph of text: "Find what you're looking for in less time. Use the following symbols to quickly modify your search term or search function". Below this text is a table with two columns: "Symbol" and "Function". The table has two rows. The first row shows the symbol "+" and the function "Finds webpages that contain all the terms that are preceded by the + symbol. Also allows you to include". The second row shows the symbol "" "" and the function "Finds the exact words in a phrase." This second row is circled in red.

Symbol	Function
+	Finds webpages that contain all the terms that are preceded by the + symbol. Also allows you to include
" "	Finds the exact words in a phrase.

The “intelligence” fallacy “AI baby-sits users.”

IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, VOL. 42, NO. 3, MARCH 2016

Metamorphic Testing for Software Quality Assessment: A Study of Search Engines

bing "Issack Newton"

41,600 RESULTS

Narrow by language ▾

[Isaac Newton - Wikipedia, the free enc](#)

en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Isaac_Newton

Sir Isaac Newton PRS
physicist and mathematician
[Life](#) · [After death](#) · [Religion](#)

[Isaac Newton - E](#)

www.biography.com/people/isaac-newton

Explore the history and life of Isaac Newton and his work in physics and optics and his group theory

[Isaac Newton's L](#)

www.newton.ac.uk/about

Isaac Newton's Life. Isaac Newton Resources. Overview

You don't know how to spell. But my code is smarter than you. It automatically corrects your errors!

The “intelligence” fallacy “AI baby-sits users.”

similar

[Isaac Newton - Wikipedia, the free enc](#)

en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Isaac_Newton

Sir Isaac Newton PRS
physicist and mathema
Life · After death · Reli

[Isaac Newton - E](#)

www.biography.com

Explore the history and
and optics and his grou

[Isaac Newton's l](#)

www.newton.ac.uk

Isaac Newton's Life. Is
Newton Resources. Ov

**And you don't even
need to know this
correction!**

Self-driving cars

<http://apollo.auto/platform/perception.html>

On the ground

- Streets and roads: much more complex and variable than airways
- Greater challenge for automation
- Greater challenge for testing.

The Uber fatal accident

On March 18, 2018, Elaine Herzberg became the first pedestrian in the world to be killed by an autonomous vehicle. <https://www.chicagotribune.com/news/columnists/wisniewski/96360037-132.html>

The Uber fatal accident

SELF-DRIVING SAFETY —

Uber escapes criminal charges for 2018 self-driving death in Arizona

The driver of the Uber vehicle could still face criminal charges.

TIMOTHY B. LEE - 3/6/2019, 1:40 PM

Outline

- The “intelligence” fallacy
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- The “reliability” fallacy
- The “safety driver” fallacy
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The “testers can always decide” fallacy

- The Uber accident revealed some of the difficulties in testing critical autonomous systems
 - an “oracle problem”.

Testing challenge: The oracle problem

- Testers need to run large numbers of tests and **verify** the test results.
- Oracle: A mechanism against which testers can decide whether the outcomes are correct.
- Oracle problem: oracle is unavailable, or difficulty to apply.
 - e.g. compilers, search engines.

Testing challenge: The oracle problem

- On-road test:
 - very limited; and
 - “humans monitoring an automated system are likely to become bored and disengaged,” which makes this kind of testing “particularly dangerous.”
 - The Uber “safety driver” did not do any safety monitoring.

Testing challenge: The oracle problem

- Much more testing is done by simulation. How can we automate the test oracle ?
 - apart from looking for collisions ...
 - Did the car overlook any obstacle?
 - To create detailed system specifications against which the autonomous vehicle's behavior can be checked involves recreating the logic of a **human driver's** decision making.

Testing challenge: The oracle problem

- Example
 - Obstacle perception

Testing challenge: The oracle problem

Perception demonstration

<http://apollo.auto/platform/perception.html>

Testing challenge: The oracle problem

Perception
demonstration:
3D LiDAR point cloud

<http://apollo.auto/platform/perception.html>

“no crash”
doesn’t
imply
correct
behavior,
because the
car may
still
overlook
obstacles –
you never
know.

Metamorphic testing

Basic principle

- Looks at **multiple** executions to see if they satisfy some expected relations
 - Metamorphic Relations
- Alleviates the oracle problem
- The new perspective of MT has detected previously unknown bugs in many mature systems.

year	# of papers
2018	(38)
2017	(28)
2016	(32)
2015	(22)
2014	(15)
2013	(18)
2012	(14)
2011	(18)
2010	(13)
2009	(12)
2008	(4)
2007	(7)
2006	(4)
2005	(8)
2004	(3)
2003	(3)
2002	(2)
2001	(1)

Metamorphic testing Publication trend (source: Scopus)

Metamorphic testing

Industry interest & adoption: Examples

Metamorphic testing of autonomous drones

M. Lindvall et al.,
"Metamorphic model-based testing of autonomous systems," ICSE Workshop on Metamorphic Testing, 2017.

Metamorphic testing of DNN models

Violations — epoch model

<https://deeplearningtest.github.io/deepTest/>

Y. Tian et al., “DeepTest: Automated testing of deep-neural-network-driven autonomous cars,” ICSE ’18. (U. of Virginia & Columbia U.)

Metamorphic testing of DNN models

(a) Snow

(b) Rain

Figure 2: Snowy and rainy scenes synthesized by DeepRoad

M. Zhang et al., “DeepRoad: GAN-based metamorphic testing and input validation framework for autonomous driving systems”, ASE ’18. (U. of Texas at Austin/Dallas, & SUST)

Metamorphic testing of DNN models

DeepTest

DeepRoad

by applying Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)

also validating input images by measuring distance to training images

Observation

- Metamorphic testing (MT) has become a standard solution to testing autonomous/AI systems
 - drones/cars/robots ...
 - all types of machine learning models/apps
- Most studies assume test oracles.
 - with MT, researchers should consider how to extend their studies by removing the oracle assumption.
 - with MT, a reviewer may now ask whether authors have considered using MT to extend their methods.

Observation

- Identifying metamorphic relations
 - Through levels of abstractions
 - Top-down
 - Bottom-up

Z.Q. Zhou, L. Sun, T.Y. Chen, and D. Towey, “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

- Segura et al. opened the research direction on metamorphic relation patterns.

IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, VOL. 44, NO. 11, NOVEMBER 2018

1083

Metamorphic Testing of RESTful Web APIs

Sergio Segura

Metamorphic relation patterns

- We further investigated the notion and formally defined the general concept of “metamorphic relation pattern (MRP)”.

Z.Q. Zhou, L. Sun, T.Y. Chen, and D. Towey, “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Definition 1: A metamorphic relation pattern (MRP) is an abstraction that characterizes a set of (possibly infinitely many) metamorphic relations.

Metamorphic relation patterns

- and two specific MRPs: “symmetry” and “asymmetry”.

Z.Q. Zhou, L. Sun, T.Y. Chen, and D. Towey, “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Definition 2: The *symmetry MRP* refers to the existence of different viewpoints from which the system appears the same.

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

American inventors - Google Search - Mozilla Firefox

American inventors - Google X +

https://www.google.com/search?dcr=0&source=hp&q=American+inventors&oq=American+inventors&gs_l=psy-ab.3..35i39k

Google American inventors

All Images News Videos Books More Settings Tools

Inventors > United States

<p>Elijah McCoy 1844-1929</p>				
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Zhi Quan Zhou et al., “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

美国发明家 - Google Search - Mozilla Firefox

美国发明家 - Google Search × +

https://www.google.com/search?dcr=0&q=美国发明家&oq=美国发明家&gs_l=psy-ab.3..35i39k1.442906.442906.0.445142.1.

Google

美国发明家

All Images News Maps Videos More Settings Tools

Inventors > United States

<p>Robert H. Goddard 1882–1945</p>				
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Zhi Quan Zhou et al., “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

The screenshot shows a Google Translate search for the Chinese phrase "translate 我爱吃苹果". The search results are displayed under the "Web" tab. The search shows 168,000,000 results. The source language is set to "Chinese Simplified" and the target language is "English". The translation shown is "I love to eat", which is an incorrect and incomplete translation of the original Chinese text "我爱吃苹果".

168,000,000 Results Date ▾ Language ▾ Region ▾

Chinese Simplified ▾ ⇌ English ▾

我爱吃苹果 Edit I love to eat

Data from: [Microsoft Translator](#)

Zhi Quan Zhou et al., “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Translator interface. At the top, there are two dropdown menus: 'English' on the left and 'Chinese Simplified' on the right, with a double-headed arrow between them. Below the menus, the English text 'I love to eat' is displayed in a large font. To its right, the Chinese translation is shown as '我爱吃' (wǒ ài chī). The Chinese text is significantly shorter than the English text, illustrating a lack of symmetry in the translation. There is an 'Edit' button above the English text and a speaker icon above the Chinese text.

Data from: [Microsoft Translator](#)

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

amazon **Try Prime** All ▾ women dress 🔍

Departments ▾ Your Amazon.com Today's Deals Gift Cards & Registry Sell EN 🌐

1-48 of 160 results for "women dress"

Sort by Price: Low to High ▾

This screenshot shows the Amazon search interface for the query "women dress". The search bar contains "women dress" and the search button is highlighted. Below the search bar, the text "1-48 of 160 results for 'women dress'" is displayed. The "Sort by" dropdown menu is set to "Price: Low to High" and is circled in red.

amazon **Try Prime** All ▾ women dress 🔍

Departments ▾ Your Amazon.com Today's Deals Gift Cards & Registry Sell EN 🌐

1-48 of 851,077 results for "women dress"

Sort by Price: High to Low ▾

This screenshot shows the Amazon search interface for the query "women dress". The search bar contains "women dress" and the search button is highlighted. Below the search bar, the text "1-48 of 851,077 results for 'women dress'" is displayed. The "Sort by" dropdown menu is set to "Price: High to Low" and is circled in red.

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

Portcullis House to 67 Bridge St, London SW1A 2PW, UK - Google Maps - Mozilla Firefox

Portcullis House to 67 Bridge X +

https://www.google.com/maps/dir/Portcullis+House,+1+Parliament+St,+Westmins

Portcullis House, 1 Parliament St, Westr

67 Bridge St, London SW1A 2PW, UK

Add destination

OPTIONS

Send directions to your phone

via Bridge St/A302
Mostly flat

1 min
3 ft

DETAILS

Zhi Quan Zhou et al., “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

67 Bridge St, London SW1A 2PW, UK to Portcullis House - Google Maps - Mozilla Firefox

67 Bridge St, London SW1A 2PW, UK

Portcullis House, 1 Parliament St, Westminster

Add destination

OPTIONS

Send directions to your phone

via Victoria Embankment/A3211 and A3212

10 min
0.5 mile

This route has restricted usage or includes private roads.
Mostly flat

DETAILS

Zhi Quan Zhou et al., “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

Fig. 24: Examples of MR violations.

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

Video Labels

Detect objects, such as dog, flower, human, in the entire video.

Note: shot-level label annotations are present on the shots tab.

(a) Four objects were detected in the original video.

Zhi Quan Zhou et al., “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

Video Labels

Detect objects, such as dog, flower, human, in the entire video.

Note: shot-level label annotations are present on the shots tab.

(b) Five objects were detected in the backwards-played video.

Zhi Quan Zhou et al., “Metamorphic relations for enhancing system understanding and use,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2018.2876433>

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

J. Brown, Z. Q. Zhou, and Y.-W. Chow, “Metamorphic testing of navigation software: A pilot study with Google Maps,” in Proceedings of the 51st Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS-51), 2018, pp. 5687–5696, available: <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/50602>.

Metamorphic relation patterns

Examples of detected issues against “symmetry”

J. Brown, Z. Q. Zhou, and Y.-W. Chow, “Metamorphic testing of navigation software: A pilot study with Google Maps,” in Proceedings of the 51st Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS-51), 2018, pp. 5687–5696, available: <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/50602>.

Metamorphic relation patterns

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Outline

- The “intelligence” fallacy
- The “testers can always decide” fallacy
- **The “reliability” fallacy**
- The “safety driver” fallacy
- More examples of detected bugs

The “reliability” fallacy

- It is widely believed that “machine learning applications are generally reliable when the input is similar to the training data.”

The “reliability” fallacy

DOI:10.1145/3241979

Metamorphic testing can test untestable software, detecting fatal errors in autonomous vehicles' onboard computer systems.

BY ZHI QUAN ZHOU AND LIQUN SUN

Metamorphic Testing of Driverless Cars

The “reliability” fallacy

Real-life
Baidu
Apollo
LiDAR
Perception
Module.

Z.Q. Zhou and L. Sun, “Metamorphic testing of driverless cars,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 61–67, March 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3241979>

The “reliability” fallacy

1000 random points

Introducing a “noise” MR pattern, a sub-pattern under “symmetry”.

Z.Q. Zhou and L. Sun, “Metamorphic testing of driverless cars,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 61–67, March 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3241979>

The “reliability” fallacy

Z.Q. Zhou and L. Sun, “Metamorphic testing of driverless cars,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 61–67, March 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3241979>

The “reliability” fallacy

A few mosquitos
can crash the car.

10 random points

Z.Q. Zhou and L. Sun, “Metamorphic testing of driverless cars,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 61–67, March 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3241979>

The “reliability” fallacy

In addition, “obstacle type” also changed, e.g. from “unknown” to “car”, or from “car” to “cyclist”.

The “reliability” fallacy

- We reported the findings to the Apollo self-driving car team **eight days before** the Uber accident.

- Apollo and Uber use exactly the same LiDAR sensor, Velodyne’s HDL64E
- We did not receive a response until 24 hours after the Uber accident.
- In its reply, the Apollo perception team confirmed the issue.

PRELIMINARY REPORT

HIGHWAY

HWY18MH010

The information in this report is preliminary and will be supplemented or corrected during the course of the investigation.

Figure 1. (Left) Location of the crash on northbound Mill Avenue, showing the paths of the pedestrian in orange and of the Uber test vehicle in green. (Right) Postcrash view of the Uber test vehicle, showing damage to the right front side.

PRELIMINARY REPORT

HIGHWAY

HWY18MH010

The information in this report is preliminary and will be supplemented or corrected during the course of the investigation.

According to data obtained from the self-driving system, the system first registered radar and LIDAR observations of the pedestrian about 6 seconds before impact, when the vehicle was traveling at 43 mph. As the vehicle and pedestrian paths converged, the self-driving system software classified the pedestrian as an unknown object, as a vehicle, and then as a bicycle with varying expectations of future travel path. At 1.3 seconds before impact, the self-driving system determined that an emergency braking maneuver was needed to mitigate a collision (see figure 2).² According to Uber, emergency braking maneuvers are not enabled while the vehicle is under computer control, to reduce the potential for erratic vehicle behavior. The vehicle operator is relied on to intervene and take action. The system is not designed to alert the operator.

What ?!

Outline

- The “intelligence” fallacy
- The “testers can always decide” fallacy
- The “reliability” fallacy
- **The “safety driver” fallacy**
- More examples of detected bugs

The “safety driver” fallacy

- Does a safer system bring better safety?
 - Not necessarily.
 - We must consider human factors
 - Pilots are used to being looked after by AI.
 - Now AI suddenly throws an “emergency” to humans
 - can humans quickly understand it?
 - can humans quickly handle it?

Pilots has under 40 seconds to override the malfunctioning system.

CNN World » Africa | Americas | Asia | Australia | China | Europe | Middle East | India | UK Live TV U.S. Ed

NYT: Pilots had 40 seconds to avert disaster in test of Boeing 737 Max plane

By Jack Guy, CNN
Updated 6:31 AM ET, Wed March 27, 2019

The “safety driver” fallacy

- Does “reporting to pilot” solve all problems?
 - Uber “safety driver” was not monitoring
 - Boeing to issue 737 Max 8 “software fix”:
 - When two sensors disagree, AI shall give control to pilot.
 - How about “warning sensor” is true, “OK sensor” is wrong?
 - How about the two sensors agree but both are wrong ?
 - Boeing has NOT solved the problem!
 - Metamorphic relations for sensor data could help.
 - Air France Flight 447's harrowing end
 - Faulty speed sensors disagreed (frozen)
 - Autopilot disengaged
 - Pilots didn't know how to properly drive.

The “safety driver” fallacy

- Ongoing work
 - Sensor data validation using metamorphic relations.

Outline

- The “intelligence” fallacy
- The “testers can always decide” fallacy
- The “reliability” fallacy
- The “safety driver” fallacy
- **More examples of detected bugs**

Instance of “Noise” pattern: Tesla

The screenshot shows the IEEE Spectrum website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'Join IEEE', 'IEEE.org', 'IEEE Xplore Digital Library', 'IEEE Standards', 'IEEE Spectrum', and 'More Sites'. On the right side of the top bar are 'Create Account' and 'Sign In' links. Below the navigation bar is a banner advertisement for IEEE with the text: "IEEE has different things to offer you at different stages of your career." and "Discover what IEEE can do for your career." with a 'Join Today' button. The main content area features the IEEE SPECTRUM logo and a menu with 'Engineering Topics', 'Special Reports', 'Blogs', 'Multimedia', 'The Magazine', 'Professional Resources', and 'Search'. A red horizontal bar contains the text 'Cars That Think | Transportation | Self-Driving'. Below this, the article title is 'Three Small Stickers in Intersection Can Cause Tesla Autopilot to Swerve Into Wrong Lane', dated '1 Apr 2019 | 10:56 GMT'. The subtitle reads: 'Security researchers from Tencent have demonstrated a way to use physical attacks to spoof Tesla's autopilot'. The author is 'By Evan Ackerman'. A video player is embedded at the bottom, showing a Tesla's interior dashboard with a speedometer at 30. A circular inset in the video shows a close-up of a road surface with three small white stickers. A large purple circle with a white 'G' is overlaid on the left side of the video player, along with standard video controls (play, stop, close, refresh).

<https://spectrum.ieee.org/cars-that-think/transportation/self-driving/three-small-stickers-on-road-can-steer-tesla-autopilot-into-oncoming-lane>

<https://youtu.be/6QSsKy0I9LE>

Instance of “Replace” pattern Google AI Translation

Source Language: English (en) | Target Language: Chinese (Simplified) (zh)

Source Text: Tom is a go-getter.

Target Text: 汤姆是个干干净净的人。

which means
“Tom is a
clean person.”

C. Wu, L. Sun, and Z.Q. Zhou, “The impact of a dot: Case studies of a noise metamorphic relation pattern,” in ICSE MET ’19.

Instance of “Replace” pattern Google AI Translation

The screenshot shows the Google Cloud Translate interface. The source language is English (en) and the target language is Chinese (Simplified) (zh). The source text is "Trump is a go-getter." The word "Trump" is circled in red. A red arrow labeled "replace" points from the word "go-getter" in the source text to the Chinese translation "特朗普是一个吸毒者。".

which means “Trump is a drug addict.”

Instance of “Noise” pattern Google AI Translation

which means “Trump is a vampire.”

Source Language: English (en) | Target Language: Chinese (Simplified) (zh)

Source text: Trump is a go-getter..

Target text: 特朗普是一个吸血鬼..

noise

Source Language: English (en) | Target Language: Chinese (Simplified) (zh)

Source text: Trump is a go-getter.....

Target text: 特朗普是一个不错的选择.....

noise

which means “Trump is a good choice.”

We have detected this bug and reported to Apollo in Dec 2018, who soon released a new version in Jan 2019 (v3.5)

Collision with obstacle at 1'8"

(video: Apollo version 3.0)

We then detected further bugs in v3.5, in Jan 2019

Car suddenly brakes.

(video: Apollo version 3.5)

Questions are welcome

